

Making Sense of the Environmental Science Landscape: An Exploration of the CEEDER Database

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INTRODUCTION

To support evidence-based policy making, decision makers rely on synthesis of relevant research. Evidence in policy-briefs can become a key source of information for non-experts (Haddaway et al., 2014). In the environmental sciences, the Collaboration for Environmental Evidence's Database for Evidence Reviews (CEEDER), a curated repository of almost 2000 reviews, aims to inform decision makers (Konno et al. 2020). Evidence reviews collected within the database are only as reliable as their included data (Haddaway et al., 2014). Policies are likewise tied to the quality of the reviews they are based on, but this dependency carries more gravity because of the immediate real-world consequences (Gurevitch et al., 2018). CEEDER communicates how much confidence decision-makers should place on reviews by categorizing each review with a rating of gold, green, amber, or red, provided by experts unaffiliated with a review's authors. In addition, the database supports users in discovering relevant research. A built-in query interface allows users to filter CEEDER by collections and with Boolean search strings. Yet these options are only effective for users whose evidence needs are known in advance. Discovery options are limited: no effort is made to put the reviews in relation to one another, consolidating their findings to provide a comprehensive overview of the broader environmental science landscape, and the underlying data structure holding all reviews, a static CSV file (CEEDER, 2024), struggles to paint the bigger picture. Our exploration of the CEEDER database aims to provide policy makers, researchers and the public, with an accessible and actionable overview of environmental science by externalizing scientometric data like citation relationships through visualizations such as networks and word clouds.

METHODS

First, we parse the database dump CSV file (retrieved on August 2, 2024) to extract the Title, Review Question, and Link for each review. To limit the amount of data to process, we restrict ourselves to the 356 reviews¹ in the climate change collection, by applying a CEEDER search filter. Using the review's DOI from the Link column, we query the OpenAlex API to retrieve each review's metadata, including its references. We then calculate a similarity network (Fig. 1) based on relative bibliographic coupling strength (Shen et al., 2019), with the evidence reviews as nodes and the similarity value between them as edges. An edge is only shown if the encoded similarity value is greater than zero, with the edge width proportional to the similarity value. We then apply the Leiden community detection algorithm (Traag et al., 2019) and color the nodes according to their community affiliation with a fixed color coding. Finally, using the segmentation of the network into communities, we count how often a concept is mentioned in the research questions for that community's reviews. We visualize the occurrence ranking in word clouds (Fig. 2), removing stop words to focus on the scientific content. The size of a concept within a cloud reflects its number of occurrences.

Our source code is available on GitHub².

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

Fig. 1 shows a similarity network with one large cluster in the center, a small cluster on the lower left, and a handful of distributed reviews that connect to parts of the central cluster. Not shown are fewer outliers that

Fig. 1: The similarity network of references as nodes with similarity values as edge width and community affiliation by node coloring

¹ 336 after removing duplicate entries and broken or missing source links

² https://github.com/infoqualitylab/CEEDER_study

In the future, more complex computations, such as embeddings, could help validate our interpretations or hint toward new directions. We also aim to consider the freshness of recently published information and quality ratings provided by CEEDER. Finally, because the quality of a review depends on its included studies, we would like to extract only included studies. Differentiating between types of references is important. Not every reference truly counts, for instance reviews may cite negative examples without including them in their synthesis.

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REFERENCES

- Collaboration for Environmental Evidence. (2021). CEEDER Database – Environmental Evidence. Retrieved August 2, 2024, from <https://environmentalevidence.org/ceder-search/>
- Falkowski, P., Scholes, R. J., Boyle, E., Canadell, J., Canfield, D., Elser, J., Gruber, N., Hibbard, K., Högberg, P., Linder, S., Mackenzie, F. T., Moore, B., 3rd, Pedersen, T., Rosenthal, Y., Seitzinger, S., Smetacek, V., & Steffen, W. (2000). The global carbon cycle: a test of our knowledge of earth as a system. *Science (New York, N.Y.)*, 290(5490), 291–296. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.290.5490.291>
- Gough, D., Oliver, S., & Thomas, J. (2017). *An introduction to systematic reviews* (2nd ed.). SAGE.
- Gurevitch, J., Koricheva, J., Nakagawa, S., & Stewart, G. (2018). Meta-analysis and the science of research synthesis. *Nature*, 555(7695), 175–182. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature25753>
- Haddaway, N. R., & Pullin, A. S. (2014). The policy role of systematic reviews: Past, present and future. *Springer Science Reviews*, 2(1–2), 179–183. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40362-014-0023-1>
- Hedges, L. V., Gurevitch, J., & Curtis, P. S. (1999). The meta-analysis of response ratios in experimental ecology. *Ecology*, 80(4), 1150–1156. <https://doi.org/10.2307/177062>
- Konno, K., Cheng, S. H., Eales, J., Frampton, G., Kohl, C., Livoreil, B., Macura, B., O'Leary, B. C., Randall, N. P., Taylor, J. J., Woodcock, P., & Pullin, A. S. (2020). The CEEDER database of evidence reviews: An open-access evidence service for researchers and decision-makers. *Environmental Science & Policy*, 114, 256–262. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2020.08.021>
- Shen, S., Zhu, D., Rousseau, R., Su, X., & Wang, D. (2019). A refined method for computing bibliographic coupling strengths. *Journal of Informetrics*, 13(2), 605–615. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.joi.2019.01.012>
- Traag, V. A., Waltman, L., & van Eck, N. J. (2019). From Louvain to Leiden: Guaranteeing well-connected communities. *Scientific Reports*, 9(1), 5233. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-019-41695-z>